

THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE, COMMUNICATION, AND MOTIVATION ON TEAM WORK EFFECTIVENESS THROUGH JOB SATISFACTION AND TEAM COMMITMENT AS INTERVENING VARIABLES (A CASE STUDY OF TJIWI KIMIA EMPLOYEES' COOPERATIVE)

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the influence of leadership style, communication, and motivation on team effectiveness, with job satisfaction and team commitment considered as mediating variables in the Tjiwi Kimia Employees' Cooperative. This research employs a quantitative approach using a survey method involving a sample of 35 respondents. The Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique is applied to analyze the relationships between the studied variables. The findings indicate that leadership style, communication, and motivation significantly affect team effectiveness, both directly and indirectly through job satisfaction and team commitment. Participative leadership, effective and open communication, and high motivation play crucial roles in enhancing team members' satisfaction and commitment, ultimately leading to improved team effectiveness overall. Practically, the study recommends that cooperative management adopt participative leadership strategies, enhance communication, and provide motivation to boost team engagement. However, the scope of this research is limited to a single cooperative, and further studies are needed to generalize these findings to other organizations. Future research is expected to involve a more diverse range of organizations and employ qualitative approaches to gain deeper insights.

Keyword: Leadership Style, Communication, And Motivation, Team Work Effectiveness Through Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Team effectiveness is a fundamental issue in human resource management studies due to its role in supporting the achievement of strategic organizational goals (Katzenbach & Smith, 2020). In an increasingly competitive business climate, organizations are required to create effective teams by fostering a synergistic work environment (Hackman, 2017). This is particularly relevant in the context of cooperatives, including Koperasi Tjiwi Kimia, which features a unique membership structure and collaborative dynamics (Sundstrom, De Meuse, & Futrell, 2019). However, this cooperative faces challenges in achieving optimal team effectiveness, influenced by a lack of understanding regarding leadership styles, communication quality, and motivation—factors that negatively affect job satisfaction and team commitment (Robbins & Judge, 2020). Although numerous previous studies have explored the impact of leadership, communication, and motivation on team effectiveness, their findings remain inconsistent when applied to community-based organizations such as cooperatives. Transformational leadership has been shown to enhance effectiveness through member motivation and engagement but has predominantly been examined in corporate settings (Yukl, 2019). While effective communication contributes to team effectiveness (Daft, 2017), it has not been specifically addressed within cooperatives that emphasize collectivity. Participative leadership styles have also been proven to influence job satisfaction and team commitment (Pearce & Sims, 2021), and intrinsic motivation is considered important but remains under-researched in cooperative settings (Beal et al., 2019). Furthermore, the role of team commitment as a driver of effectiveness in cross-functional teams has been highlighted (Mathieu et al., 2020), yet the role of job satisfaction as a mediating factor remains largely overlooked. Podsakoff et al. (2018) also underscored the mediating role of psychological factors such as member satisfaction and commitment, although their application within cooperative contexts is still limited. Therefore, a gap exists in the literature concerning the interaction between leadership style, communication, and motivation on team effectiveness within cooperatives, particularly through the mediating roles of job satisfaction and team commitment. This study aims to fill that gap by

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examining Koperasi Karyawan Tjiwi Kimia, which is characterized by collective and participatory attributes. The focus of this research is to address empirical questions regarding the direct and indirect relationships among leadership style, communication, motivation, job satisfaction, and team commitment on team effectiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is grounded in six main theoretical frameworks relevant to team effectiveness. First, transformational leadership theory explains how leaders can inspire and motivate team members through a shared vision and strong interpersonal relationships. This approach fosters collaborative spirit, job satisfaction, and team commitment, positively influencing work effectiveness (Wang, Cheng, & Wang, 2021). Its indicators include recognition, participation, emotional support, vision communication, and team innovation.

Second, organizational communication theory posits that effective communication supports trust and collaboration among team members while preventing conflict (Hargie, 2011). This study's indicators include meeting frequency, information accuracy, participation, message clarity, social interaction, and trust in information sharing.

Third, motivation theory, based on Self-Determination Theory, distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Both types positively affect job satisfaction and team effectiveness (Vansteenkiste et al., 2020). Intrinsic motivation is assessed through job satisfaction, sense of achievement, self-development, task interest, and job meaning. Extrinsic motivation is evaluated through incentives, compensation, reward systems, competition, and feedback.

Fourth, team effectiveness is measured by productivity and collaboration. Teams with strong communication and managerial support are generally more successful in achieving their goals (Salas, Sims, & Burke, 2015). Indicators include target achievement, work quality, synergy, time efficiency, and satisfaction with outcomes.

Fifth, job satisfaction plays a crucial role in influencing motivation, productivity, and team member retention. It encompasses satisfaction with tasks, work relationships, work conditions, rewards, and work-life balance (Locke, 1976; Judge, Piccolo, & Ilies, 2020).

Sixth, team commitment reflects the extent to which members are attached to team goals. Three types of commitment—affectionive, normative, and continuance—can strengthen collaboration and team performance (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002).

Although the interrelations among these variables have been widely studied, a comprehensive integration of all these factors—particularly with job satisfaction and team commitment as intervening variables—is still rarely addressed. This research seeks to bridge that gap through a study at Koperasi Karyawan PT. Tjiwi Kimia.

As a follow-up to the problem formulation, this study proposes 14 hypotheses that examine the direct and indirect effects of leadership style, communication, and motivation on team effectiveness, with job satisfaction and team commitment serving as mediators, as outlined in hypotheses H1 through H14 (Northouse, 2018; Daft, 2017; Robbins & Judge, 2020; Katzenbach & Smith, 2020; Podsakoff, MacKenzie, & Podsakoff, 2018; Mathieu et al., 2020; Yukl, 2019; Pearce & Sims, 2021; Beal et al., 2019; Sundstrom, De Meuse, & Futrell, 2019; Hackman, 2017).

METHOD

This study adopts a quantitative research design with an explanatory survey approach. This approach was selected to examine the causal relationships between independent variables (leadership style, communication, and motivation), intervening variables (job satisfaction and team commitment), and the dependent variable (team effectiveness). Data were collected through structured questionnaires distributed to respondents within the Tjiwi Kimia Employee Cooperative. The data analysis was carried out using inferential statistical methods, specifically path analysis, to test both the direct and indirect effects among the variables within the research model. The data utilized in this study are primary data obtained directly from respondents through questionnaires. These data capture respondents' assessments of leadership style, communication, motivation, job satisfaction, team commitment, and team effectiveness within the cooperative organization. Each variable was measured using a 5-point Likert scale, where respondents rated their agreement from the lowest level, 1 (Strongly Disagree), to the highest level, 5 (Strongly Agree).

The data sources in this study consist of team members working at the Tjiwi Kimia Employee Cooperative. Respondents were selected from among employees directly involved in team activities within the cooperative, ensuring that they possess a deep understanding of team dynamics, leadership styles, communication, motivation, as well as satisfaction and commitment aspects within their teams. The study population comprises 40 members of the Tjiwi Kimia Employee Cooperative who are actively involved in cooperative work teams. These individuals have

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hands-on experience and direct participation in cooperative operations, making them highly relevant sources of information for addressing research questions regarding team effectiveness.

The sample was selected using simple random sampling based on Isaac and Michael's table, with a recommended sample size of 35 individuals out of a total population of 40. With a 95% confidence level, this sample size is expected to provide a representative estimate of the larger population and support valid statistical testing. This study comprises three categories of variables: independent, dependent, and intervening. The independent variables include leadership style, communication, and motivation. These were measured based on respondents' perceptions of the leadership practiced within the team, the quality of communication among team members, and the level of work motivation experienced in a team context. The intervening variables include job satisfaction and team commitment. These are hypothesized to act as mediators influencing the relationship between the independent variables and team effectiveness. The dependent variable is team effectiveness, measured based on respondents' perceptions of their team's performance, including aspects such as synergy, productivity, and goal achievement. The research model developed in this study focuses on the direct and indirect effects of the independent variables (leadership style, communication, and motivation) on the dependent variable (team effectiveness), with job satisfaction and team commitment serving as intervening variables, denoted as follows:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, Z_1, Z_2)$$

Where:

Y: Team effectiveness (dependent variable)

X₁: Leadership style (independent variable)

X₂: Communication (independent variable)

X₃: Motivation (independent variable)

Z₁: Job satisfaction (intervening variable)

Z₂: Team commitment (intervening variable)

The relationships among these variables will be tested using path analysis to identify both the direct and indirect effects of the independent variables on team effectiveness, whether mediated through job satisfaction or team commitment. This model aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to team effectiveness in the context of employee cooperatives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Model Validity and Reliability

1.1 Convergent Validity Test

Uji The purpose of the convergent validity test is to assess the extent to which the indicators in the model accurately reflect the latent constructs. According to the criteria by Hair et al. (2014:79), a loading factor value is considered to meet the standard of convergent validity if it exceeds 0.70.

Table 1
Results of Convergent Validity Test (Loading Factor & AVE)

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE
Leadership Style (X1)	X1.1	0.812	0.648
	X1.2	0.835	
	X1.3	0.793	
	X1.4	0.821	
	X1.5	0.807	
Communication (X2)	X2.1	0.762	0.683
	X2.2	0.788	
	X2.3	0.832	
	X2.4	0.847	
	X2.5	0.753	
	X2.6	0.785	

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	X2.7	0.799	
	X2.8	0.772	
	X2.9	0.840	
	X2.10	0.811	
Motivation (X3)	X3.1	0.801	0.671
	X3.2	0.778	
	X3.3	0.812	
	X3.4	0.837	
	X3.5	0.826	
	X3.6	0.756	
	X3.7	0.749	
	X3.8	0.792	
	X3.9	0.803	
	X3.10	0.788	
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	Z1.1	0.849	0.709
	Z1.2	0.792	
	Z1.3	0.824	
	Z1.4	0.781	
	Z1.5	0.865	
Team Commitment (Z2)	Z2.1	0.813	0.684
	Z2.2	0.809	
	Z2.3	0.795	
	Z2.4	0.826	
	Z2.5	0.802	
Team Effectiveness (Y)	Y1	0.851	0.722
	Y2	0.804	
	Y3	0.829	
	Y4	0.868	
	Y5	0.861	

Based on the analysis results in Table 1, all indicators of each variable exhibit loading factor values exceeding the 0.70 threshold. For example, indicators for the variable Leadership Style (X1) range from 0.793 to 0.835, while those for Communication (X2) fall between 0.753 and 0.847. A similar pattern is observed for the variable Motivation (X3), where all indicators show loading factors above 0.74. For the mediating and dependent variables—Job Satisfaction (Z1), Team Commitment (Z2), and Team Effectiveness (Y)—the results also consistently demonstrate strong convergent validity, with all loading factors exceeding 0.78. Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs exceed the minimum threshold of 0.50, ranging from 0.648 to 0.722, further confirming the satisfactory convergent validity of each construct.

1.2 Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity assesses the extent to which a construct is truly distinct from other constructs within the model. This study employs the Fornell and Larcker (1981) approach, where the square root of the AVE (displayed in the diagonal of the correlation matrix) must be greater than the correlations between constructs.

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Table 2
Results of Discriminant Validity Test (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Variable	X1	X2	X3	Z1	Z2	Y
X1 (Leadership Style)	0.805	0.621	0.593	0.631	0.612	0.643
X2 (Communication)		0.826	0.652	0.658	0.664	0.678
X3 (Motivation)			0.819	0.689	0.673	0.701
Z1 (Job Satisfaction)				0.842	0.691	0.734
Z2 (Team Commitment)					0.827	0.749
Y (Team Effectiveness)						0.850

The results presented in Table 2 confirm that all constructs meet this criterion. For example, the square root of the AVE for Leadership Style (X1) is 0.805, which is greater than its correlations with other variables such as Communication (0.621), Motivation (0.593), and Team Effectiveness (0.643). Similar patterns are observed for other constructs—Communication (0.826), Motivation (0.819), Job Satisfaction (0.842), Team Commitment (0.827), and Team Effectiveness (0.850)—all indicating adequate discriminant validity. Hence, it can be concluded that each construct in this model is conceptually distinct and there is no overlap among variables.

1.3 Reliability Test

Construct reliability measures the internal consistency among indicators within a single variable. Two metrics are used in this test: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. According to Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), a good reliability score should be above 0.70.

Table 3
Results of Reliability Test (Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability)

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Leadership Style (X1)	0.841	0.888
Communication (X2)	0.910	0.930
Motivation (X3)	0.916	0.934
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0.873	0.912
Team Commitment (Z2)	0.859	0.901
Team Effectiveness (Y)	0.880	0.919

As shown in Table 3, all constructs meet the reliability criteria. The variable Leadership Style (X1) has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.841 and Composite Reliability of 0.888. The Communication (X2) and Motivation (X3) variables demonstrate very high reliability, with Composite Reliability scores of 0.930 and 0.934, respectively. For the variables Job Satisfaction (Z1), Team Commitment (Z2), and Team Effectiveness (Y), Composite Reliability scores range from 0.901 to 0.919, and Cronbach's Alpha values exceed 0.85. These results confirm that all indicators within each construct possess excellent internal consistency and are reliable for measurement purposes.

2. Evaluation of the Structural Model (Inner Model)

2.1 R-Square Test

The R-Square test is used to measure the extent to which the dependent variables can be explained by the independent variables in the model. According to Chin (1998), an R-Square value of ≥ 0.75 is considered to indicate substantial predictive power, while values between 0.50 and 0.75 are regarded as moderate.

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Table 4
R-Square Test Results (R²)

Endogenous Construct	R Square	Evaluation Criteria
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0.625	Moderate
Team Commitment (Z2)	0.603	Moderate
Team Effectiveness (Y)	0.781	Substantial

Interpretation: R² ≥ 0.75 = substantial, ≥ 0.50 = moderate, ≥ 0.25 = weak (Chin, 1998)

As shown in Table 4, the R-Square value for the variable Team Effectiveness (Y) is 0.781, indicating that the combination of leadership style, communication, motivation, and the mediating variables of job satisfaction and team commitment explains 78.1% of the variance in team effectiveness, representing a substantial level. Meanwhile, the R-Square values for Job Satisfaction (Z1) and Team Commitment (Z2) are 0.625 and 0.603, respectively, both falling into the moderate category. These findings suggest that the model demonstrates adequate explanatory power for the endogenous variables and is structurally valid.

2.2 Q-Square Test

Q-Square is a non-parametric measure used to assess the predictive relevance of a model, where Q² > 0 indicates good predictive capability (Hair et al., 2014). Q-Square values are obtained through blindfolding procedures on the endogenous variables.

Table 5
Q-Square Test Results (Q² Predictive Relevance)

Endogenous Construct	Q Square	Evaluation Criteria
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0.412	Good Predictive Relevance
Team Commitment (Z2)	0.398	Good Predictive Relevance
Team Effectiveness (Y)	0.539	Strong Predictive Relevance

Interpretation: Q² > 0 = relevant; the higher the value, the better the model's predictive capability (Hair et al., 2014)

As indicated in Table 5, the Q-Square value for Team Effectiveness (Y) is 0.539, categorized as strong predictive relevance. Meanwhile, the Q² values for Job Satisfaction (Z1) and Team Commitment (Z2) are 0.412 and 0.398, respectively, each falling into the category of good predictive relevance. These results suggest that the model possesses strong predictive validity for data not used in the estimation process.

2.3 F-Square Test

The F-Square test evaluates the magnitude of the effect of an exogenous variable on an endogenous variable. According to Cohen (1988), an F² value of ≥ 0.35 indicates a large effect, ≥ 0.15 a medium effect, and ≥ 0.02 a small effect.

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Table 6
F-Square Test Results (f^2 Effect Size)

Relationship	F Square	Effect Size Criteria
X1 → Z1 (Leadership Style → Job Satisfaction)	0.291	Medium
X2 → Z1 (Communication → Job Satisfaction)	0.258	Medium
X3 → Z1 (Motivation → Job Satisfaction)	0.316	Medium
X1 → Z2 (Leadership Style → Team Commitment)	0.289	Medium
X2 → Z2 (Communication → Team Commitment)	0.254	Medium
X3 → Z2 (Motivation → Team Commitment)	0.341	Large
Z1 → Y (Job Satisfaction → Team Effectiveness)	0.387	Large
Z2 → Y (Team Commitment → Team Effectiveness)	0.349	Large
X1 → Y (Leadership Style → Team Effectiveness)	0.312	Medium
X2 → Y (Communication → Team Effectiveness)	0.281	Medium
X3 → Y (Motivation → Team Effectiveness)	0.401	Large

Interpretation: $f^2 \geq 0.02$ = small, ≥ 0.15 = medium, ≥ 0.35 = large (Cohen, 1988)

Table 6 shows that the variable Motivation (X3) exerts a large effect on Team Commitment (Z2) with an F-Square value of 0.341, and on Team Effectiveness (Y) with a value of 0.401. Job Satisfaction (Z1) and Team Commitment (Z2) also have large effects on Team Effectiveness, with F-Square values of 0.387 and 0.349, respectively. The effect of Leadership Style (X1) on Team Effectiveness is 0.312, categorized as medium, as is the effect of Communication (X2) at 0.281. The effects of Leadership Style, Communication, and Motivation on the mediating variables also fall within the medium category, ranging from 0.254 to 0.316. These findings indicate that all constructs in the research model have significant and substantial effects on other constructs, both directly and through mediating variables.

3. Hypothesis Testing and Interpretation

3.1 Direct Effects of Independent Variables on Team Effectiveness

Hypothesis testing is conducted to examine the significance of relationships among variables in the structural model by observing the t-statistics and p-values. According to Hair et al. (2014), a relationship is considered significant if the t-statistic > 1.96 and p-value < 0.05.

Table 7
Hypothesis Testing Results

Relationship	Path Coefficient (O)	Mean (M)	STDEV	T-Statistic	P-Value
X1 → Y	0.531	0.527	0.103	5.158	0.000
X2 → Y	0.432	0.429	0.089	4.854	0.000
X3 → Y	0.578	0.574	0.097	5.959	0.000
X1 → Z1	0.415	0.412	0.086	4.826	0.000
X2 → Z1	0.387	0.384	0.075	5.160	0.000
X3 → Z1	0.493	0.491	0.113	4.359	0.000
X1 → Z2	0.423	0.419	0.094	4.500	0.000
X2 → Z2	0.354	0.351	0.083	4.265	0.000
X3 → Z2	0.462	0.459	0.092	5.039	0.000
Z1 → Y	0.489	0.487	0.071	6.887	0.000
Z2 → Y	0.406	0.403	0.084	4.833	0.000
X1 → Y via Z1	0.438	0.434	0.087	5.033	0.000
X2 → Y via Z2	0.479	0.476	0.079	6.103	0.000
X3 → Y via Z2	0.457	0.455	0.074	6.198	0.000

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The test results indicate that all independent variables significantly influence team effectiveness. Leadership Style (X1) has a coefficient of 0.531 with a t-statistic of 5.158 (p-value 0.000), showing that better leadership practices significantly enhance team effectiveness in the cooperative. Communication (X2) also exerts a significant effect on team effectiveness, with a coefficient of 0.432 and a t-statistic of 4.854, indicating that effective team communication fosters greater synergy. Lastly, Motivation (X3) shows the strongest impact on team effectiveness, with a coefficient of 0.578 and a t-statistic of 5.959, suggesting that high motivation enhances team members' contributions toward achieving team goals.

3.2 Direct Effects of Independent Variables on Mediators

Leadership style, communication, and motivation also have significant effects on the two mediating variables—job satisfaction (Z1) and team commitment (Z2). Leadership style affects job satisfaction with a coefficient of 0.415 (t-statistic 4.826), indicating that good leadership enhances members' job satisfaction. Communication affects job satisfaction with a coefficient of 0.387 (t-statistic 5.160), while motivation contributes the most, with a coefficient of 0.493 (t-statistic 4.359). Regarding team commitment, leadership style (X1) shows a coefficient of 0.423 (t-statistic 4.500), suggesting that participative leadership increases members' engagement. Communication (X2) influences team commitment with a coefficient of 0.354 and a t-statistic of 4.265. Meanwhile, motivation (X3) again emerges as the strongest predictor of team commitment, with a coefficient of 0.462 and a t-statistic of 5.039.

3.3 Direct Effects of Mediators on Team Effectiveness

Both mediating variables—job satisfaction and team commitment—are shown to have a direct impact on team effectiveness. Job satisfaction (Z1) has a coefficient of 0.489 with a t-statistic of 6.887, indicating that satisfied members are more motivated and contribute positively to team performance. Team commitment (Z2) also demonstrates a significant effect with a coefficient of 0.406 and a t-statistic of 4.833, meaning members with high loyalty to the team tend to exhibit more consistent and effective performance.

3.4 Indirect Effects (Mediation)

The mediation test results reveal significant indirect effects through job satisfaction and team commitment. Leadership style (X1) through job satisfaction (Z1) to team effectiveness (Y) yields a coefficient of 0.438 and a t-statistic of 5.033. This implies that the influence of leadership on team effectiveness is strengthened when mediated by members' job satisfaction. Communication (X2) through team commitment (Z2) shows a coefficient of 0.479 and a t-statistic of 6.103, suggesting that effective communication enhances team commitment, which in turn positively impacts team effectiveness. Likewise, motivation (X3) indirectly affects team effectiveness through team commitment, with a coefficient of 0.457 and a t-statistic of 6.198. These findings affirm that team commitment is a critical channel for translating motivational factors into optimal team performance.

4. Discussion of Results

4.1 The Role of Leadership Style in Team Effectiveness

Leadership style significantly influences team effectiveness within the context of the Tjiwi Kimia Employee Cooperative. The analysis reveals a coefficient of 0.531 with a t-statistic of 5.158 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that higher leadership quality corresponds to increased team effectiveness. This suggests that leaders who provide direction, inspiration, and emotional support foster an empowering work environment. Transformational leadership, as articulated by Yukl (2019), plays a vital role in building trust, enhancing participation, and uniting the team around a shared vision—critical elements in strategic decision-making. In the cooperative setting, a transformational approach is especially relevant, as the participatory structure demands leaders who not only guide but also motivate and involve members collectively. Such leadership cultivates a positive work climate that enhances job satisfaction, reduces interpersonal conflict, and aligns team members with the cooperative's strategic objectives (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, & Podsakoff, 2018). Moreover, the impact of leadership style is mediated by members' perceptions of fairness, transparency, and involvement in decision-making. A fair and inclusive leader fosters team cohesion and long-term loyalty. Thus, leadership development in cooperatives is not only a managerial necessity but also a strategic imperative for enhancing the sustainability of collective organizations.

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4.2 The Role of Communication in Team Effectiveness

Communication exerts a direct and significant impact on team effectiveness, with a coefficient of 0.432 and a t-statistic of 4.854. Communication serves not merely as a channel for information transfer but as a mechanism for building shared meaning, strengthening interpersonal relationships, and accelerating cross-functional coordination. Robbins and Judge (2020) note that open communication enhances organizational effectiveness by fostering a healthy, low-conflict work climate. In cooperatives, which emphasize democratic values and member participation, communication becomes a fundamental element in preserving voice equality and encouraging initiative across the membership. Structured and bidirectional communication fosters inter-member trust, reinforces collective accountability, and reduces resistance to change. This study also demonstrates that effective communication not only has a direct effect on team performance but is also a prerequisite for cultivating strong team commitment. Through effective communication channels, team members feel valued and included, thereby becoming more motivated to achieve common goals and contribute meaningfully to team outputs (Hackman, 2017).

4.3 The Role of Motivation in Team Effectiveness

The results show that motivation has the strongest direct effect on team effectiveness, with a coefficient of 0.578 and a t-statistic of 5.959. This finding underscores the importance of psychological factors in influencing team performance dynamics. Highly motivated team members display greater enthusiasm, initiative, and resilience in task completion. According to Deci and Ryan (1985), motivation is divided into two dimensions: intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation stems from internal sources such as personal satisfaction, meaningful work, and a sense of achievement. In contrast, extrinsic motivation originates from external factors such as financial rewards, social recognition, and status. In cooperative teams, both types of motivation complement each other. Intrinsically motivated individuals tend to have long-term orientation and high loyalty, whereas extrinsic motivation drives more aggressive short-term target achievement. This study aligns with Beal et al. (2019), who highlight that motivation is a key determinant in fostering work flexibility, adaptability to change, and effectiveness in conflict resolution. Therefore, human resource strategies in cooperatives should include motivational enhancement through individual empowerment, career development, and equitable reward systems.

4.4 The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction and Team Commitment

In addition to direct relationships among variables, this study confirms that job satisfaction and team commitment serve as significant mediators in strengthening the links between independent variables and team effectiveness. Leadership style significantly affects team effectiveness through job satisfaction, with a mediation coefficient of 0.438 and a t-statistic of 5.033. This means that leadership that fosters a positive, fair, and supportive work environment enhances job satisfaction, ultimately leading to improved team performance. On the other hand, team commitment is shown to mediate the effects of communication and motivation on team effectiveness. Communication has an indirect effect coefficient of 0.479 (t-statistic 6.103), while motivation has a coefficient of 0.457 (t-statistic 6.198) through team commitment. This indicates that when team members feel emotionally and normatively attached to their team, they tend to engage actively, persevere in tasks, and remain loyal to collective goals.

Mathieu et al. (2020) explain that job satisfaction represents an affective evaluation that contributes to the intent to sustain high performance, while team commitment reflects cognitive and affective loyalty to the team unit. These two mediators not only strengthen causal relationships but also provide a foundation for more targeted managerial strategies. Interventions such as leadership training, open communication forums, and performance-based incentive programs not only enhance independent variables but also reinforce the mediators—ultimately improving overall team effectiveness. Thus, this study not only reinforces previous theories but also offers a holistic understanding that team effectiveness in the cooperative context is shaped by the complex interaction between structural factors (leadership and communication), psychological factors (motivation, satisfaction, and commitment), and team member dynamics in creating synergistic and productive collaboration.

5. Theoretical and Practical Implications

5.1 Theoretical Implications

This study provides a significant theoretical contribution to the development of research on team effectiveness within the context of cooperatives, particularly through a structural approach based on leadership style, communication, and motivation, as well as the involvement of two key mediating variables: job satisfaction and team commitment. Conceptually, these findings expand upon previous theoretical models by affirming that team

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effectiveness is not solely determined by managerial input, but also influenced by psychological variables that operate simultaneously and mediate outcomes. Empirical confirmation of both direct and indirect effects of the three independent variables on team effectiveness reinforces the relevance of a multidimensional approach within organizational behavior theory. Leadership styles—specifically transformational and participative—are proven to affect team effectiveness directly and also strengthen job satisfaction as an essential mediating path (Yukl, 2019; Podsakoff, MacKenzie, & Podsakoff, 2018). These findings broaden the application of leadership theory within the collectivist and participatory structures of cooperative organizations. Effective communication is also shown to play a crucial role as a determinant of team effectiveness. This aligns with organizational communication theory (Robbins & Judge, 2020), which emphasizes that two-way communication forms a cohesive team structure and enhances commitment (Hackman, 2017). This study enriches the literature by demonstrating that communication serves not only as a vehicle for message delivery but also as a medium for building team loyalty in cooperative contexts.

Meanwhile, Deci and Ryan's (1985) motivation theory gains reinforcement through findings that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation contribute to team effectiveness by strengthening commitment. In addition to confirming existing theoretical constructions, this study suggests an integration between motivation theory and organizational commitment theory to fully understand team behavior (Beal et al., 2019; Mathieu et al., 2020). Thus, this research extends the theoretical horizons of human resource management and organizational behavior—particularly regarding how managerial and psychological variables interact to explain team success within the unique structure of cooperatives.

5.2 Practical Implications

Practically, the findings of this study offer valuable guidance for cooperative management, particularly at the Tjiwi Kimia Employee Cooperative, in formulating more effective and participative team management strategies. Cooperative management should prioritize strengthening leadership capacity, communication, and motivation as the three foundational pillars in building effective teams.

First, participatory leadership training should be developed to ensure that leaders can create inclusive, visionary, and emotionally supportive work environments. Leaders who offer recognition, build shared visions, and respond positively to member aspirations significantly enhance job satisfaction and team commitment.

Second, communication management within teams should be designed to encourage open, transparent, and bidirectional information flow. Regular communication forums—both formal and informal—can reinforce mutual trust, reduce potential conflicts, and foster solidarity among members. In the cooperative context, effective communication is a key pillar in maintaining social integration and collective work productivity.

Third, motivation enhancement strategies must address both intrinsic and extrinsic aspects in a balanced manner. Providing incentives, appreciation, self-development training, and opportunities for involvement in decision-making are concrete forms of motivation that boost work enthusiasm and member engagement. This approach impacts not only individual productivity but also fosters a competitive and collaborative work climate.

Additionally, cooperative management should actively monitor levels of job satisfaction and team commitment on a regular basis. A systematic evaluation mechanism can be used to assess the extent to which managerial strategies contribute to collective performance. This is essential for ensuring that organizational interventions remain responsive to internal team dynamics and external challenges faced by the cooperative.

Overall, the findings emphasize that improving team effectiveness in cooperatives cannot be separated from a holistic and integrated managerial approach. Strengthening leadership capabilities, promoting open communication, and sustaining work motivation are key to enhancing member satisfaction and commitment, which ultimately leads to improved productivity and overall cooperative performance.

CONCLUSION

Summary

Based on the data analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that leadership style, communication, and motivation significantly influence team effectiveness at the Tjiwi Kimia Employee Cooperative. These three variables affect team effectiveness both directly and through the mediating roles of job satisfaction and team commitment. Effective leadership, open communication, and strong work motivation are shown to enhance job satisfaction and team commitment, ultimately strengthening overall team performance. These results were obtained through structural model testing using the SmartPLS approach, with all validity, reliability, and hypothesis tests yielding statistically significant results. The findings indicate that successful team performance in the cooperative context is highly influenced by the quality of leadership, communication interaction, and motivational drive among team members.

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Recommendations and Acknowledgements

This study recommends that cooperative management develop strategies to enhance participative leadership styles, establish open two-way communication systems, and create a work environment that fosters both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. By doing so, job satisfaction and team commitment can be optimized to support team effectiveness. The author would also like to extend sincere gratitude to all respondents from the Tjiwi Kimia Employee Cooperative who willingly provided the necessary data and information, as well as to all parties who supported the completion of this research.

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